

Corona of Thorns and Crown of Glory

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CCOVID-19 or Corona—crown, in Latin—has capped and crippled nations with a virulent virus that has brought everyone to their knees. Almost everyone today is reflecting, praying, and seeking remedies to right wrongs. I’ve never felt so helpless, homebound; yet, as a religionist, I’m hopeful that ‘religion’—from the Latin *religare*, meaning, ‘to bind’—will bind us more tightly to God, mother earth and each other during this ‘home-bound’ period. So, let’s reflect upon the corona-crowns that we have wrongly conferred or conveniently condoned.

The Crown of God

Crown is a rich biblical symbol with many meanings, positive and negative. First, crowns are used for the enthronement of Israel’s kings and queens (2 Kings 11:12; 1 Chron 20:2; 2 Chron 23:11; Esther 2:17; 8:15). Second, though the ruler wears the crown, it’s actually God, Universal Ruler, who “sets a crown of fine gold on his head” (Ps 21:3); hence the king is but God’s representative, expected to reign as God would. Third, if the king forgets his subordinate relationship with God, God denounces him for he has “defiled his crown in the dust” (Ps 89:39). Fourth, rulers in authority must realize their finitude and frailty: “for riches do not last forever, nor a crown for all generations” (Prov 27:24).

These **References** clearly teach us that crowns belong solely to God, the Ultimate Sovereign, who creates, sustains, and nurtures everything and everyone in the cosmos. In a beautiful hymn “Great is your name, Lord,” based on psalm 8, the psalmist says of human beings, “You have made them a little less than God, and crowned them with glory and honour” (Ps 8:5). As created beings, instead of glorifying God, have we not dethroned God and crowned ourselves as demigods making money, manipulating markets, grabbing power? These crowns have crumbled.

“You have made them a little less than God, and crowned them with glory and honour”

Jesus teaches us that God is Spirit and Truth—accessible anytime, everywhere, by everyone—in his conversation with the Samaritan woman (Jn 4:23). Though despised by others, Jesus frees her from manmade categories. In gratitude, she spreads the good news of her encounter with him, and brings her whole village to proclaim that Jesus is: “truly, the Saviour of the world” (Jn 4:42). We have hitherto felt secure worshipping God in churches. Now, rather than bemoaning the shutdown of churches, may we feel at home with God, realizing that our homes are ‘domestic churches’.

In the ‘domestic church’ which is my home, let me pilgrimage inside, deep into *‘who’* is deepest within me—the God-gifted ‘I’ that, according to the Bible, is an image of God. This true ‘self’ is not the same as the ‘Ego’ that seeks to grab things selfishly for itself, always relating with others for self-interest. It’s time now to discover what St Augustine called *‘intimior intimo meo’*—that which is ‘deeper than my own depths’. This true self must flourish with right relationships.

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The Crown of Thorns

WhatsApp has been keeping us abreast of what’s happening, worldwide. We’ve seen clips of robots serving food in Wuhan, Korean medicos dressed like astronauts to cure the sick, Europeans gasping for breath in overcrowded ICUs and Californians rushing to buy guns, should goods run out and goons run amuck. These heartrending snapshots have enforced social distancing. However, isn’t social distancing something we’ve mastered ages ago? Often, our societal crowns are clear-cut: ‘I’ above all else; We versus They; male over female; patriot versus antinational; insiders against outsiders. What we’re sheepishly seeing now is the concretization of our infected minds.

Coronaviruses don’t distinguish between President and pauper. Today, UK’s Prince Charles and PM Boris Johnson are self-isolated, weak and powerless, just like other victims. This reminds us that the air we breathe and the waters we bathe in are one, while coronary arteries universally have same blood-groups, positive or negative. Mother earth invites us to inhale fresh air and savour the once-silenced symphony of insects and birds. The swans at Venice and otters of Singapore are reclaiming their habitats. Homebound humanity has birthed clearer skies, cleaner seas, saner surroundings, fruitfulness of flora, freedom for fauna. Be glad, be grateful.

We are currently in the period of Lent—literally meaning ‘springtime’—in preparation for the Holy Week of Jesus’ passion and death. The excruciating crown that was thrust upon Jesus’ head was braided together with thorns, mockingly placed with a “Hail, king of the Jews!” jibe (Jn 19:3). Beaten, bloody and broken, Jesus is then brought face-to-face with another

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crowned character: Pontius Pilate. Captive Christ stands tall with his inner, spiritual authority, while Roman Governor Pilate brags of his imperial power. Christ is crowned with thorns; Pilate is clad in gold. While Jesus is bathed in blood, Pilate washes his bloodied hands, declaring, “I am innocent of this man’s blood; see to it yourselves!” (Mt 27:24)

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Today, not only Christians but peoples of the whole world feel crowned with thorns, tired and tense—not knowing when all of this will end. The light at the end of the tunnel is nowhere in sight. Perhaps, these days in the runup to Holy Saturday, the masks, handwashes, sanitizers, closedowns and distances call for unmasking of pretenses, soul-cleansing, purging of prejudices, openness and intimacy with God, with others, with mother earth and with our deepest self. As Christians, life does not end with death but with eternal life.

Conclusion: Crown of Glory

In conclusion, let’s remember that, besides the aforementioned crowns, apostle Paul speaks of the “crown of righteousness” (2 Tim 4:8) that awaits those who are faithful to Christ. Moreover, apostles James and John describe the “crown of life” for those who love God and persevere under trials (Jas 1:12; Rev 2:10). Let us never lose hope! Covid-19 imposes a crown of thorns upon our swollen heads, but our cooperation, compassion and co-vitality throughout 2020 might raise us, not mere victims but victors over Corona – destroying our manmade, infected coronations, too – to attain that “crown of glory” (1 Pet 5:4) promised by the Crucified-Risen Christ, who will wear the “golden crown” (Rev 14:14). He alone will rule forever! I wish you a Happy Easter, too!